

**Open Research Case Study
Lancaster University**

Putting the 'R' into Open Research: the transformation of research data skills for students in Psychology

John Towse (Psychology, Lancaster University)

Tom Beesley (Psychology, Lancaster University)

Amy Atkinson (Psychology, Lancaster University)

Rob Davies (Psychology, Lancaster University)

Margriet Groen (Psychology, Lancaster University)

Matthew Ivory (Psychology, Lancaster University)

Emma Mills (Psychology, Lancaster University)

[on behalf of the Dept of Psychology, Lancaster University]

Putting the 'R' into Open Research: the transformation of research data skills for students in Psychology

Our bid centres around the Psychology department and community support for embedding reproducible analysis in research. In particular the uptake of R as an open source, shareable, reproducible statistical engine for data science and the use of GitHub as a repository and educational resource.

Since 2020, the Department of Psychology have rolled out R as the principal software vehicle for teaching data science to Undergraduate, Masters, and PhD students. Staff had already adopted R for Masters level data science training in previous years, but this marked both the wholesale deployment across our teaching curriculum, and the complete redevelopment and re-imagining of the way students learn about and are supported in their data analysis training. This substantial shift to the open science platform went hand-in-hand with our established commitment to open science practice exemplified by the PROSPR group. In doing so, we fundamentally refocused the student perspective on how data ideas can be integrated into research processes as well as treating them as transferable soft skills for graduate employability.

Whilst the kernel of change we describe is the promotion of an open source, reproducible, software engine, our use case goes much broader and deeper. Because of the formal reproducible nature of the workflow, the implications of the change involve a large reframing of what data skills mean for the student experience, and the relationships between research analysis both as a user and a creator of research data. Indeed, this has allowed Psychology to develop a roadmap for students' journey in developing a portfolio of statistical skills (see below).

Due to the changes in the way that R functions (in comparison to legacy applications such as SPSS), when we introduced R, we also rebuilt the research methods curriculum to teach in a more innovative way, by being more structured and more experience-based from a student perspective. We also sought to more closely integrate our tuition across years and across programs, providing a comprehensive workbook of tuition material (<https://lu-psy-r.github.io/>). This created a more dynamic and practical set of materials, where students can easily revisit and revise content as they

progress in their training, and that assists the practical steps of their data, as they move towards the challenge of completing their R analysis in the student dissertation research project work in their final year.

Similarly, we have taken advantage of an R server to create and deliver shiny apps - interactive web pages that can provide demonstrations, showcase code and R functionality, and organise student quizzes. These represent one example of several types of teaching materials have been developed, built around and hosted via GitHub. This allows us to create shared documents (amongst staff), bring multimedia resources to help students experience R, and develop bespoke but consistent educational activities that reduce student anxieties about working with data and working with code. Over the course of an undergraduate degree, we build foundations of data science, build confidence and develop competence in reproducible analysis (see roadmap above). We have also connected this transformation of undergraduate teaching to graduate programmes that help students extend their mastery of working in open, reproducible data science. Together, these then form an enduring and stable reference guide for students across their degree journey, so they can refer back to previous work long after the teaching sessions have been completed.

Our focus as a department has been on providing a rewarding experience for our own students in mastering data science skills for a more open research ecosystem. We are one of a growing number of departments that have transitioned away from “closed” software practices. We have been proactive in discussing the opportunities and the lessons learned from our experiences for the benefit of other UK departments and further afield. We organised the first national seminar / webinar to discuss R teaching in Psychology, and contributed to the second event held at Nottingham Trent University

With R being an open source, scalable, ecosystem of packages, staff have also developed and released analytic tools for behavioural research such as eye-tracking, in the form of eyetools. Amongst a range of objectives, eyetools makes accessible and simplifies research processing choices for students and researchers alike to make sense of a variety of research data.

References

Psychology student analysis guide <https://lu-psy-r.github.io>

Examples of You Tube recordings of national discussion of teaching analysis to Psychology students

First presentation at the Lancaster seminar, 2021, <https://youtu.be/VfmisntqcqE>

Lancaster presentations at the NTU seminar, 2022: https://youtu.be/X9VaH-_Pg94 &

<https://youtu.be/ehjM-om7U1Y>

Eyetools: <https://tombeesley.github.io/eyetools/>

<http://DOI.org//10.5281/zenodo.19693359>